

Evaluation of Fertility Response and Transient Sterility Following N-Ethyl-N-Nitrosourea Exposure in Male Japanese Quails

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Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

In Nigeria, Japanese quail production faces significant challenges due to the bird's small size, which results in low meat yield and limited consumer acceptance. These constraints highlight the need for genomic improvement strategies aimed at enhancing economically important traits such as body size. As an initial step toward genomic improvement, this study investigated whether administering N-ethyl-N-nitrosourea (ENU) as a chemical mutagen could induce transient sterility in male Japanese quails—a critical marker of successful germline mutagenesis. A total of ninety male Japanese quails were randomly assigned to one of three groups for this study: an ENU treatment group, a sham shock solution control group, and a normal saline control group. Each group received its respective treatment solution via intraperitoneal injection, with dosages adjusted according to individual body weights and administered once a week for three consecutive weeks. Fertility and semen quality parameters were evaluated both before and after the treatments. Specifically, the ENU-treated cocks were injected with a total dose of 300 mg ENU per kilogram of body weight, delivered in

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three weekly fractions of 100 mg ENU/kg. Fertility in ENU-treated cocks decreased significantly during weeks 1, 2, and 3 post-treatment, but no significant differences were observed from weeks 4 to 6. Although there was an early decline in fertility, transient sterility was not induced, as fertility remained relatively high. Semen quality parameters showed no statistically significant differences between ENU-treated and control cocks. The study concludes that the dosage regimen was insufficient to induce transient sterility in Japanese quail cocks, suggesting that species-specific reproductive physiology, particularly the rapid spermatogenic cycle of Japanese quail, may restrict the mutagen's effectiveness. To address these limitations, future research should explore alternative dosing strategies that account for the species-specific characteristics of Japanese quails.

Keywords: *N-ethyl-N-nitrosourea; Japanese quail; transient sterility; semen; fertility; mutagenesis.*

1. Introduction

Following their official introduction into Nigeria by the National Veterinary Research Institute (NVRI) in 1992, Japanese quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) have enjoyed a continual increase in economic significance, predominantly within the country's expanding poultry subsector (Saka et al., 2018). Although Japanese quail farming initially showed great potential in Nigeria, interest in it has waned considerably in recent years due to a combination of economic, structural, and informational challenges (Adeoti and Baruwa, 2019; Adebayo et al., 2023; Maidala et al., 2024). One of the main obstacles is the lack of consumer awareness and acceptance of quail products, which limits market demand and deters ongoing investments (Adeoti and Baruwa, 2019; Mnisi et al., 2021; Odafe and Nojuvwevwo, 2021; Maidala et al., 2024). Among the challenges hindering the acceptance of quail products are the perceived low meat yield, absence of processing facilities, economic concerns for farmers, and consumer preferences (Adeoti and Baruwa, 2019; Gbadamosi et al., 2024). Most of these drawbacks are primarily correlated with bird size, and enhancing it could significantly highlight its natural advantages over other poultry species.

To address the challenges associated with bird size and its impact on the acceptance of quail products, this study explores whether chemical mutagenesis, as a genomic improvement strategy, can be effectively applied to Japanese quails. Specifically, it explored N-ethyl-N-Nitrosourea (ENU), an alkylating agent extensively used in genetic research to induce mutations. It functions by transferring ethyl groups to nucleophilic sites in DNA, leading to various types of mutations; particularly point mutations such as, Adenine/ Thymine to Thymine/ Adenine (A/T-to-T/A) or Guanine/ Cytosine to Cytosine/ Guanine (G/C-to-C/G) transversion mutations, and or Adenine to Guanine or Cytosine to Thymine (A ↔ G or C ↔ T) transition mutations randomly throughout the genome in mice and other organisms (Justice et al., 1999; Borisova et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2022; Varlamova et al., 2023; LeBlanc et al., 2025). Its mutagenesis has been shown to be useful in the determination of the genetic architecture of quantitative traits in studies of animal models of human diseases (Toye et al., 2004; Toye, 2013; Varlamova et al., 2023). Additionally, recent studies have demonstrated the utility of ENU for defining the genetic architecture of quantitative traits in livestock (Adesina et al., 2017; Hai et al., 2017; Adesina, 2018; Cao et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2020; Adesina et al., 2024). Taken together, ENU has been shown to be capable of inducing quantitative trait variation in treated animal groups. This suggests that ENU can be utilised to generate new genetic variability, enabling selection for improvement even in animal populations where traditional selection methods have reached their limits.

In N-ethyl-N-nitrosourea (ENU) mutagenesis programmes, transient sterility following administration of the mutagen is a major indicator of successful mutagenesis (Nolan et al., 1997; Imai et al., 2021; Yan and Shen, 2022). Successful mutagenesis typically provides a basis for investigating collections of potential mutants, enabling researchers to study mutations in specific genes of interest using genomic approaches or to examine variants in traits through phenotypic analysis (Nguyen et al., 2011; Toye, 2013). In most studies, ENU is usually administered at 300 mg/kg body weight in three separate doses at one dose of 100 mg/kg body weight per week; or as a single shot of 300 mg/kg body weight depending on the animal or strain of animal (Justice et al., 1999; Coghill et al., 2002; Nguyen et al., 2011; Toye, 2013; Wang et al., 2015; Weatherly et al., 2021). Similar doses and regimes have proved effective in studies using Yoruba-Ecotype Nigerian Local Chickens (Y-NLC) (Adesina et al., 2017, 2024). Adesina et al. (2024) demonstrated that 300 mg ENU/kg body weight administered in three equal fractions over three weeks produced transient sterility and recovery in Y-NLC. The observed transient sterility and recovery by Adesina et al. (2024) is important because ENU acts on spermatogonia stem

cells, causing successfully mutagenized animals to become temporarily sterile. Typically, in successful mutagenesis protocols, spermatogenesis is temporarily halted for 10–15 weeks, regardless of the dosage or treatment regimen. During this period, surviving mutagenized spermatogonia stem cells gradually repopulate the testes, resume mitosis and meiosis within the seminiferous tubules, and ultimately generate clones of mutant sperm capable of transmitting genetic alterations to subsequent generations (Justice et al., 2000; Caignard et al., 2014; Masumura et al., 2016).

Therefore, the aim of this study was to assess whether the established ENU mutagenesis protocol could successfully induce mutagenesis in Japanese quails. To achieve this, male Japanese quails were subjected to a three-week regimen of fractionated ENU doses totalling 300 mg per kilogram of body weight, as outlined by Adesina et al. (2024). The fertility response and semen quality parameters were evaluated to determine both the duration of any induced transient sterility and the subsequent recovery period. This approach represents a preliminary step towards utilising ENU mutagenesis as a genomic improvement strategy for Japanese quail.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Safety Protocol and Ethics Statement

All experimental protocols were conducted in compliance with institutional guidelines on safe use of N-Ethyl-N-Nitrosourea (Salinger and Justice, 2008). Institutional ethical approval license was sought and obtained from the University of Ilorin Ethical Review Committee.

2.2 Experimental Birds

Three hundred and fifty Japanese quail chicks were raised until sexual maturity at age week 6. Then, 90 cocks and 120 hens were randomly selected for the study from this cohort. The cocks were divided into three groups of 30: an ENU treatment group, a sham shock solution control group, and a normal saline control group. At week eight, ten cocks from each group were chosen based on their response to the teaser female semen collection method (Chełmońska et al., 2008). These cocks were pair-housed with hens at a ratio of 1:2 for baseline and weekly post ENU administration fertility testing.

2.3 Preparation of N-Ethyl-N-Nitrosourea (ENU) and Sham (Negative Control) Shocks

N-Ethyl-N-nitrosourea was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, United Kingdom. Briefly, 1 g of the extract was dissolved in 5 ml of 95% ethanol to yield a 10x working stock concentration (200 mg/ml). The 10x working stock was diluted with 0.1 M Phosphate buffer (pH 6.0) at a ratio of 1:9 to produce an ENU stock (x1) concentration of 20 mg ENU /ml (Salinger and Justice, 2008). Sham shock solution was prepared by mixing 1 ml normal saline (0.9% NaCl in double-distilled water (ddH₂O)) with 5 ml 95% ethanol (10x sham shock concentration) and diluted with 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.0) at a ratio of 1:9 to yield a sham shock (x1) containing 0 mg ENU/ ml (Adesina et al., 2017, 2024).

2.4 Administration of ENU, Sham Shock Solution, and Normal Saline Solution

At 9 weeks of age, 30 cocks were administered a 20 mg ENU /ml stock to yield 0.1 mg ENU per gram (or 100 mg/kg) of body weight once a week for three consecutive weeks, while the control group of another 30 cocks was administered a sham shock solution containing 0 mg ENU/ ml during the same period (Adesina et al., 2017, 2024). The third group (another control group) was administered normal saline (0.9% NaCl in ddH₂O). Each cock was weighed prior to each weekly dose to determine the volume of the ENU and control solution to be injected. Thereafter, each cock was administered with an intraperitoneal injection of ENU or control solution into the abdominal area at an angle of 45° between the keel of the sternum and pubis bone using a disposable syringe fitted with a 26-gauge needle. The same crystalline batch of ENU, kept in a desiccator under refrigeration (-20 °C), was used throughout the study. All injections were completed within 3 hours of chemical dissolution, and fresh stocks of ENU were prepared before each weekly intraperitoneal injection (Adesina et al., 2017, 2024).

2.5 Semen Parameters Evaluation

Semen parameters, including semen volume, morphology, sperm motility and sperm cell concentration per volume (μl) were measured on 30 cocks: 10 cocks from each treatment group. Semen parameters were collected one week before ENU administration, and one week after ENU administration was completed.

Briefly, semen volume was determined with the aid of a micropipette fitted with a rubber tube (Thélie et al., 2019), and the volume was measured and approximated to the nearest 10 μl . Sperm motility was evaluated by estimating the percentage of sperm cells showing forward movement from 5 μl of semen on a warm glass slide with a cover slip at 400x magnification under a microscope (Churchill et al., 2014). After that, sperm concentration was determined using a “Neubaur” haemocytometer after staining with eosin 3% NaCl solution at a ratio of 1:250 and observing 400x magnification under a microscope (Chelmonska et al., 2007; Peters et al., 2008; Churchill et al., 2014). The sperm cell concentration per volume (ml) was then calculated with the following formula:

$$C = 50,000 \times N \times D$$

Where,

C = Sperm cell concentration per volume (ml)

N = Number of sperm cells counted

D = Dilution rate

Next, the morphology of spermatozoa was studied in nigrosine-eosin smears (Chelmonska et al., 2007). In every smear (under 100 \times oil immersion objective), 300 spermatozoa were counted (50 spermatozoa in each of 6 microscopic fields) and categorised into 7 classes; among them, 6 classes of live unstained spermatozoa would be regarded as total live spermatozoa (i.e., morphologically normal, bent-neck, mid-piece deformed spermatozoa, detached head, spermatozoa with other deformities), as well as dead spermatozoa stained by eosin were examined.

2.6 Fertility Test

Ten cocks from each group (previously evaluated for semen parameters) were pair-housed with hens at a ratio of 1:2 for baseline and weekly post-evaluation fertility testing, with constant mating monitored. All eggs laid by each pair of hens over five days post-mating (10 eggs per cock) were collected and incubated for fertility assessment. On the eighth day of incubation, the eggs were cracked to determine fertility—those displaying blood vessels or signs of cellular development (Chen et al., 2019) were counted as fertile. Fertility counts were recorded one week before ENU administration and weekly from week 1 to week 6 after completion of ENU dosing. Fertility data were not collected during administration due to cock lethargy and isolation for recovery.

2.7 Statistical Analysis

The effect of ENU treatment on fertility was analysed using a one-way ANOVA as appropriate for a Completely Randomised Design experiment. Means and standard errors within each treatment group were calculated thereafter. Significant means were further separated using Duncan’s multiple range test.

Next, semen volume and sperm cell concentration per millilitre underwent normality testing via the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and variance equality assessment through Levene’s test. As the data notably deviated from a normal distribution and exhibited heterogeneous variance, a non-parametric Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon rank sum test was employed for analysis (Mann and Whitney, 1947; Smirnov, 1948; Levene, 1960; Noether, 1992; Stephens, 1992).

The effect of ENU treatment on semen parameters was assessed by comparing the semen parameters of each control group, i.e., the Sham Shock Solution group and Normal Saline Solution group, to those of the ENU group in a pairwise comparison using the Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon rank sum test (Mann and Whitney, 1947). This ascertains if the tested samples are derived from the same population i.e., the population has the same shape. The Mann-Whitney U test uses a test statistic denoted as U , which represents the smaller of the two statistics U_1 and U_2 .

$$U_1 = n_1n_2 + \frac{n_1(n_1 + 1)}{2} - R_1$$

$$U_2 = n_1n_2 + \frac{n_2(n_2 + 1)}{2} - R_2$$

Where,

R_1 = Sum of ranks for group 1, and

R_2 = Sum of ranks for group 2.

In order to conduct a two-tailed test on each treatment group pair (i.e., ENU group x Sham Shock Solution group, and ENU group x Normal Saline Solution group), the observed value of the U was compared with the U value derived from the critical value table. There will be no significant differences between the two compared treatment groups if the observed value of U is less than or equal to the critical value. Thus, a significant difference between the ENU and the Sham Shock Solution groups or the Normal Saline groups indicated a semen quality difference. The effect size was determined as described by Field (2009):

$$r = \frac{Z}{\sqrt{N}}$$

Where,

r = Effect Size,

Z = Z value from the Test Statistic Table, and

N = Sample Size.

3. Results

3.1 Effect of 300 mg ENU/kg Body Weight on the Fertility of Japanese Quail Cocks

Prior to intraperitoneal injections (i.e., at week 0), fertility did not differ among the ENU, sham shock solution control (SSC), and normal saline control (NSC) groups, as all groups recorded similar fertility values of approximately 9.1 fertile eggs. Following ENU administration, fertility was significantly reduced in the ENU-treated cocks during weeks 1, 2, and 3 compared with both control groups. The lowest fertility value in the ENU group occurred in week 1 ($p = 0.00001$), with a mean of 7.0 ± 0.26 , while SSC and NSC recorded 8.8 ± 0.13 and 9.2 ± 0.13 , respectively. Significant differences were also observed in week 2 ($p = 0.025$) and week 3 ($p = 0.03$). However, as the weeks progressed, fertility in the ENU group gradually recovered, and by weeks 4, 5, and 6, there was no longer a significant difference in fertility compared to the control groups. Fertility in the ENU group increased to 9.2 ± 0.13 in week 4 and remained comparable to the control groups through weeks 5 and 6. Summarily, ENU treatment caused a temporary reduction in fertility during the first three weeks post-administration, followed by recovery to control-level fertility by week 4 (Table 1).

3.2 Effect of 300 mg ENU/kg Body Weight on the Semen Parameters of Japanese Quail Cocks

ENU administration did not significantly affect the semen parameters of Japanese quail cocks (Tables 2, 3, and 4). The comparison between the ENU and sham shock solution control (SSC) groups showed no significant differences ($p > 0.05$) in morphology, dead cells, motility, sluggish sperm cells, sperm concentration, or semen volume. Although motility was numerically higher in the ENU group than in the SSC group, the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2). Similarly, there were no significant differences between the ENU and normal saline control (NSC) groups across all semen parameters. Morphology, motility, and sperm concentration were numerically lower in the ENU group than in the NSC group, while dead cells and sluggish sperm cells were slightly higher in the ENU group. However, these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Semen volume was lower in the ENU group than in the NSC group, but the difference was not significant ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

Table 1. Effect of 300 mg ENU/kg on fertility in Japanese quail cocks from week 0 - 6 of ENU administration

	Week 0	Week 1	Week 2	Week 3	Week 4	Week 5	Week 6
Treatment							
ENU	9.1 ± 0.23 (10)	7 ± 0.26 ^a (10)	8.8 ± 0.2 ^a (10)	9 ± 0 ^a (10)	9.2 ± 0.13 (10)	9.4 ± 0.16 (10)	9.6 ± 0.16 (10)
SSC	9.1 ± 0.23 (10)	8.8 ± 0.13 ^b (10)	9.4 ± 0.16 ^b (10)	9.5 ± 0.22 ^b (10)	9.6 ± 0.16 (10)	9.6 ± 0.16 (10)	9.7 ± 0.15 (10)
NSC	9.1 ± 0.18 (10)	9.2 ± 0.13 ^b (10)	9.4 ± 0.22 ^b (10)	9.6 ± 0.16 ^b (10)	9.5 ± 0.17 (10)	9.6 ± 0.16 (10)	9.7 ± 0.15 (10)
P-Values	1	0.0001	0.025	0.03	0.18	0.61	0.87

ENU = N-ethyl-N-Nitrosourea; SSC = Sham Shock Solution Control; NSC = Normal Saline Solution Control. Data presented as percentage ± SEM and count in parentheses. Values within factor, within column with different superscript ^{abc} are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 2. Effect of 300 mg ENU/kg body weight and sham shock solution injections on the semen parameters of Japanese quail cocks

Semen Parameters	Treatment					
	ENU (n=10)	SSC (n=10)	U	Z	P	r
Morphology	0.60	0.50	33.50	-1.57	0.12	0.13
Dead Cells	0.10	0.25	31.50	-1.69	0.09	0.09
Motility	0.60	0.35	29.50	-1.86	0.06	0.07
Sluggish	0.20	0.25	38.50	-1.20	0.23	0.25
Concentration ($\times 10^7/ml$)	$80 * 10^7$	$60 * 10^7$	39.50	-1.11	0.27	0.28
Volume (μl)	20.00	20.00	54.00	-0.08	0.94	0.97

ENU = N-ethyl-N-Nitrosourea; SSC = Sham Shock Solution Control; U = Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon test statistic, Z = Z-Score, P = p-value, r = Effect size, Significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 3. Effect of 300 mg ENU/kg body weight and normal saline solution injections on the semen parameters of Japanese quail cocks

Semen Parameters	Treatment					
	ENU (n=10)	NSC (n=10)	U	Z	P	r
Morphology	0.60	0.65	45.50	-0.69	0.49	0.51
Dead Cells	0.10	0.05	46.00	-0.67	0.50	0.56
Motility	0.60	0.75	44.00	-0.81	0.42	0.47
Sluggish	0.20	0.1	44.50	-0.76	0.45	0.47
Concentration ($\times 10^7/ml$)	$80 * 10^7$	$95 * 10^7$	45.50	-0.68	0.49	0.51
Volume (μl)	20.00	30	31.00	-1.81	0.07	0.09

ENU = N-ethyl-N-Nitrosourea; NSC = Normal Saline Solution Control; U = Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon test statistic, Z = Z-Score, P = p-value, r = Effect size, Significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 4. Baseline and post-injection semen parameters of Japanese quail cocks

Semen Parameters	Period					
	Before (n=30)	After (n=30)	U	Z	P	r
Morphology	0.6	0.6	462.50	-0.26	0.79	-0.03
Dead Cells	0.1	0.1	426.50	-0.78	0.43	-0.01
Motility	0.7	0.6	429.50	-0.74	0.46	-0.09
Sluggish	0.1	0.15	417.50	-0.92	0.36	-0.12
Concentration ($\times 10^7/ml$)	$86 * 10^7$	$80 * 10^7$	411.00	-0.98	0.33	-0.12
Volume (μl)	20	20	479.00	-0.02	0.98	-0.00

N.B: U = Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon test statistic, Z = Z-Score, P = p-value, r = Effect size, Significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Semen parameters before and after injection were not significantly different (Table 4). Morphology, dead cells, and semen volume remained unchanged, while motility and sperm concentration showed slight numerical reductions after injection. Additionally, the effect sizes (r) – a statistical measure that quantifies the strength or magnitude of the relationship between two variables or the extent of an observed effect - for all parameters were small, indicating minimal practical differences within the groups. However, when comparing semen parameters post-injection between ENU and SSC, all effect sizes except for volume were negligible; semen volume had a large effect size ($r = 0.97$), but the P-value (0.94) was not statistically significant, suggesting that the large difference is probably due to random variation rather than a real effect. Similarly, when comparing semen parameters post-injection between ENU and NSC, all effect sizes were small to moderate, but the P-values were statistically insignificant; thus, the observed differences are possibly due to natural variability (Table 4). These results, therefore, indicate that 300 mg ENU/kg body weight did not produce a statistically significant change in semen quality parameters.

4. Discussion

The fertility pattern observed after ENU administration indicates that the treatment had a mild effect on fertility in Japanese quail cocks but did not produce a persistent sterility phase. In ENU mutagenesis programmes, a

sustained period of transient sterility is a key indicator of successful mutagenesis. In this study, despite a statistically significant decrease in fertility in the ENU group compared to the control groups, transient sterility was not observed, as the mean fertility count at the lowest point remained at 70% (Table 1). Thus, fractionated doses of 300 mg ENU/kg body weight did not induce mutagenesis in male Japanese quail, suggesting the administered dose regimen was not sufficient to sustain germline suppression in this species, unlike in chickens, mice, and zebrafish (Nolan et al., 1997; Wang et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2016; McAlpine et al., 2019; Aliyu et al., 2020; Balkrishna et al., 2021; Imai et al., 2021; Adesina et al., 2024; Abdulrahman et al., 2025). In chicken cocks (Yoruba Ecotype Nigeria Local Chickens), Adesina et al. (2024) reported that 300 mg ENU/kg body weight administered as described in this study induced transient sterility that lasted for 42 days. Similarly, studies in mice, such as those by Chen et al. (2016) and McAlpine et al. (2019), have shown that administering 300 mg ENU/kg body weight in weekly intervals of 100 mg allows for adequate survival and sterility while maximising the mutagenic effectiveness of ENU, as spermatogonia stem cells accumulate mutations from repeated doses over an extended period.

Furthermore, analysis of semen parameters conducted one week after ENU administration revealed no significant differences between the ENU-treated males and either control group (SSC and NSC). This absence of significant changes in semen quality suggests that the observed reduction in fertility was not attributable to noticeable alterations in ejaculate characteristics. The semen parameters recorded in this study remained in line with previously published reports describing normal semen quality in Japanese quail, further supporting the conclusion that ENU treatment did not substantially impact these traits. For example, the median semen volume was consistently 20 μ l both before and after treatment, which falls within the normal range of 5 μ l to 40 μ l for Japanese quail (Chelmonska et al., 2007; Thlie et al., 2019). Although the difference in median semen volume between the ENU (20 μ l) and NSC (30 μ l) groups after treatment was close to being significant, the variance could not be attributed to 300 mg ENU/kg treatment, as Thlie et al. (2019) also reported a varied semen volume of 5 μ l to 80 μ l, likewise, Chelmonska et al. (2007) published a variation of 20 to 35 μ l, and Chelmonska et al. (2007) recounted a variation of 15 to 26 μ l. Similarly, the median sperm concentration (80×10^7) of the cocks, also falls within the range of $5.92 - 8.12 \times 10^8$ reported by Chelmonska et al. (2007). In addition, the median score of live sperm cells that were morphologically normal for the ENU group was 60%; although this is lower than 70% - 95% reported by Chelmonska et al. (2007), it was not significantly different from that of the control groups ($p = 0.12$ for ENU x SSC and $p = 0.49$ for ENU x NSC). Also, the median score of 10% for dead cells in the ENU group followed the same trend of not being significantly different from the control groups, which puts it within the range of 83% - 99.3% live spermatozoa described in Chelmonska et al.'s (2007) study.

Summarily, this study was not able to establish a negative relation between 300 mg ENU/kg body weight treatment and semen parameters in Japanese quail cocks. Thus, it appears that ENU may have caused only a limited or fleeting reduction in fertilising capacity, without leading to any significant changes in the semen characteristics measured. Additionally, it is plausible that the timing of semen assessment was not optimal to detect potential ENU-induced effects on developing germ cells, which might have occurred during a different phase of spermatogenesis. These results, however confounding, can be explained by understanding the cycle of the seminiferous epithelium and spermatogenesis in Japanese quail; the former was reported to last for 2.69 ± 0.08 days or 64.4 ± 1.88 hours (Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean) (Lin et al., 1990). Lin et al. (1990) further concluded that there are 3.12 cycles of the seminiferous epithelium from the DNA synthesis phase of primary spermatocytes to the release of mature spermatozoa, and it was estimated that the duration between these stages is 8.39 days, although it could sometimes extend to 10 to 12 days depending on the photoperiod (Shil et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2025).

Lin and Jones (1992) (also corroborated by Hurley et al. (2018)) used the information from Lin et al. (1990) to estimate the duration and process of spermatogonia renewal. They observed that mitotic peaks of spermatogonia occur at stages II, III, VI, and IX of the seminiferous epithelium cycle. The time required for the complete renewal of all spermatogonia in quail, including type A_d stem spermatogonia, the foundational cells for spermatogenesis, was estimated to be less than 4 days. Additionally, the full spermatogenesis process, covering 4.747 cycles, was calculated to take approximately 12.77 days, from the initial division of A_d spermatogonia at the end of stage IX to the release of spermatozoa at stage V. Conversely, in chicken and mice, spermatogenesis takes 2 to 3 weeks, and 35 to 42 days, respectively (Bitencourt et al., 2007; Xie et al., 2024). This significantly varying duration of spermatogenesis could potentially explain the observed response of the Japanese quail cocks to ENU treatment in this study.

In the present study, the ENU dose administered did not affect the process of spermatogenesis, or perhaps if it did, it only affected the advanced type of spermatogonia (i.e., A_{p1}, A_{p2}, and B), leaving the primary A_d spermatogonia to continue to proliferate. Even if the A_d spermatogonia were impacted, they would have been completely renewed in less than 4 days. Furthermore, given the duration of the cycles of the seminiferous epithelium previously discussed, any epithelium tubule lesions caused by the ENU dose administered would have been almost completely renewed by the time semen was collected for analysis. Thus, it is possible that the unique reproductive physiology of Japanese quails may have resulted in the dosage regimen applied in this study being inadequate to induce mutagenesis.

5. Conclusion

The results demonstrate that administering ENU at a fractionated dose of 300 mg/kg body weight (100 mg ENU/kg each week for three weeks) resulted in a statistically significant reduction in fertility. However, the reduction in fertility observed was neither persistent nor pronounced, with the decrease reaching only up to 30%. This demonstrates that transient sterility did not occur, which is commonly viewed as a definitive sign of successful ENU mutagenesis in vertebrate models. Furthermore, the analysis of semen quality parameters revealed no statistically significant changes, indicating that the ENU dose did not affect semen quality.

Consequently, the study concludes that the ENU dosing regimen applied was insufficient to induce sustained germline disruption or observable mutagenesis in Japanese quail cocks. While minor fertility effects were detected, the lack of transient sterility and absence of significant changes in semen quality indicate that the mutagenic impact was either minimal, rapidly compensated, or confined to non-critical stages of spermatogonia development. Therefore, suggesting that species-specific reproductive physiology plays a critical role in modulating the effectiveness of ENU mutagenesis. Future studies should explore earlier semen assessment, alternative ENU dosage regimens or different developmental windows to enhance ENU mutagenic efficiency in Japanese quail.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

Author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc) and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of this manuscript.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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